

Viscosities and apparent molar volumes of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in formamide + water mixed solvents at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K

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Abstract : The apparent molar volumes (V_{ϕ}) and relative viscosities (η_{rel}) at $T = (293.15, 303.15 \text{ and } 313.15) \text{ K}$ of the solutions of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes (Li_2SO_4 , K_2SO_4 , $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, NiCl_2 , CoCl_2 , MnCl_2 , BaCl_2 , SrCl_2 , CaCl_2 , MgCl_2 , $\text{Pb}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) have been determined in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents from the measurements of densities and flow time. The partial molar volumes (V_{ϕ}^0), the coefficients A and B of Jones-Dole equation and activation thermodynamic quantities ($\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, $\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$) of viscous flow have been calculated for the solutions of these electrolytes in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents. The large positive values of V_{ϕ}^0 indicate the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions while large negative values of S_v indicate the presence of weak ion-ion interactions. Further, the positive values of viscosity B -coefficient indicate that all the electrolytes behave as structure makers in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents. This is supported by the fact that for these electrolytes, $[\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}] > 0$.

Keywords : Viscosities, molar volumes, mixed solvents.

It has been known that dielectric constant of medium plays a very important role concerning the behaviour of electrolytes in solution¹. The solvent formamide is unusual in its properties in that it is strongly self-associated through extensive network of hydrogen bond^{2,3} and its dielectric constant and dipole moment ($\epsilon = 109.5$ and $\mu = 3.68 \text{ D}$ at 298.15 K)⁴ are very high. Studies on the behaviour of electrolytes in mixed water + non-aqueous solvents have received a lot of attention in the recent past⁵⁻⁸ as precise data on electrolytes in mixed solvents find applications in many industrial processes, as they provide a wide choice of solutions with appropriate properties. With this aim in view the title study has been undertaken in the light of the following aspects :

(i) Analysis of viscosity data in respect of the solutions of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents at different temperatures in the light of Jones-Dole equation⁹

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = \eta_{rel} = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (1)$$

(ii) Ascertaining the nature of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents sys-

tem in terms of the values of coefficients A and B of Jones-Dole equation.

(iii) Determination of apparent molar volumes from density data as a function of molar concentration (C) of solutions of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and 50% formamide + water mixed solvents at different temperatures and calculation of the values of the constants V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v of Masson's equation¹⁰

$$V_{\phi} = V_{\phi}^0 + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (2)$$

and to discuss the nature of ion-ion and ion-solvent interactions on the basis of the values of V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v .

(iv) Determination of free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$, per mole of solvent and solute respectively at different temperatures and subsequent calculation of entropy and enthalpy of activation, i.e. ($\Delta S_2^{0\#}$) and ($\Delta H_2^{0\#}$).

(v) Ascertaining the structure-making or structure-breaking capacities of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents.

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Table 1. Viscosities of solutions of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in 50% formamide (FA) + water mixed solvents at different temperatures

Concentration (C) of electrolyte (mol dm ⁻³)	293.15 K		303.15 K		313.15 K	
	η (mPa.s)	$\frac{\eta_{rel}-1}{\sqrt{C}}$	η (mPa.s)	$\frac{\eta_{rel}-1}{\sqrt{C}}$	η (mPa.s)	$\frac{\eta_{rel}-1}{\sqrt{C}}$
Li ₂ SO ₄						
0.00	1.4957	-	1.2655	-	0.9895	-
0.10	1.4995	0.0220	1.2658	0.0302	0.9899	0.0203
0.25	1.5355	0.0730	1.3037	0.0806	1.0153	0.0766
0.50	1.6150	0.1287	1.3759	0.1481	1.0801	0.1530
NiCl ₂						
0.00	1.4957	-	1.2655	-	0.9895	-
0.10	1.5337	0.1081	1.2925	0.0978	1.0155	0.1177
0.20	1.6017	0.1808	1.3557	0.1831	1.0725	0.2148

Table 2. Values of coefficients A and B of Jones-Dole equation for uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in 50% formamide (FA) + water mixed solvents at different temperatures

Electrolyte	A (dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-1/2})		B (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)			
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Li ₂ SO ₄	-0.0624	-0.0628	-0.0933	0.2695	0.2899	0.3426
K ₂ SO ₄	-0.0268	-0.0719	-0.1351	0.5007	0.6272	0.8024
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	-0.0616	-0.0640	-0.0889	0.2667	0.2998	0.3398
NiCl ₂	-0.0680	-0.0997	-0.1275	0.5564	0.6276	0.7697
CoCl ₂	-0.0515	-0.1544	-0.1665	0.4744	0.6138	0.7918
MnCl ₂	-0.0704	-0.0943	-0.1112	0.3087	0.3488	0.4052
BaCl ₂	-0.0620	-0.0666	-0.1000	0.2920	0.3265	0.3818
SrCl ₂	-0.0505	-0.0695	-0.0796	0.1874	0.2107	0.2364
CaCl ₂	-0.0619	-0.0667	-0.1004	0.2615	0.2997	0.3474
MgCl ₂	-0.0610	-0.1044	-0.1097	0.2685	0.3470	0.3785
(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Pb	-0.0547	-0.0910	-0.1081	0.3854	0.4475	0.7084
Co(NO ₃) ₂	-0.0522	-0.0708	-0.0781	0.2443	0.2686	0.2804
Zn(NO ₃) ₂	-0.0581	-0.0829	-0.0986	0.3371	0.3787	0.4290
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	-0.0214	-0.0524	-0.0718	0.5233	0.5539	0.5644
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	-0.0065	-0.0211	-0.0294	0.3491	0.3706	0.4007
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	-0.0512	-0.0741	-0.0895	0.2584	0.2942	0.3469

Results and discussion

The viscosities of solutions of electrolytes in 50% (v/v) formamide (FA) + water mixed solvents have been determined as a function of molar concentration (C) at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K and the representative data in respect of Li₂SO₄ (uni-bivalent electrolyte) and NiCl₂ (bi-univalent electrolyte) have been presented in Table 1. The viscosity data have been analyzed in the light of Jones-Dole equation.

The values of coefficients A and B have been obtained from the linear plots of $(\eta_{rel} - 1)\sqrt{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} (vide Fig. 1) by the method of least squares and the values have been presented in Table 2. It is seen that the values of A are negative for all the uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes which indicate the presence of weak ion-ion interactions in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents. It will not be out of place to mention here the fact that in recent years many workers¹¹⁻¹⁴ have reported negative values of A in respect of solutions of electrolytes in pure and mixed solvent systems. On the other hand, the values of coefficient B are positive for all the electrolytes. These positive values of B suggest the presence of strong ion-solvent interactions¹⁵. Further, with the rise in temperature the values of B are rendered increasingly positive. This may be ascribed to the increased solvation of ions of electrolytes in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system.

Table 3. Densities (ρ) and apparent molar volumes (V_ϕ) of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in 50% formamide (FA) + water mixed solvents at different temperatures

Concentration (C) of electrolyte (mol dm ⁻³)	ρ (g cm ⁻³)		V_ϕ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)		ρ (g cm ⁻³)		V_ϕ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	
	293.15 K		303.15 K		313.15 K			
Li ₂ SO ₄								
0.00	1.0570	-	1.0510	-	1.0482	-	-	-
0.20	1.0642	70.00	1.0560	81.09	1.0521	86.13	-	-
0.40	1.0782	53.82	1.0674	65.75	1.0641	67.00	-	-
0.50	1.0857	49.72	1.0797	50.00	1.0744	55.00	-	-
NiCl ₂								
0.00	1.0570	-	1.0510	-	1.0482	-	-	-
0.10	1.0646	152.56	1.0567	171.78	1.0535	176.64	-	-
0.20	1.0756	136.94	1.0657	156.43	1.0626	158.00	-	-

The values of apparent molar volume (V_ϕ) in respect of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system have been determined as a function of molar concentration from density data, at 293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K using the following expression :

$$V_\phi = \frac{1000(\rho_0 - \rho)}{C \rho_0} + \frac{M}{\rho_0} \tag{3}$$

where C is the molarity of the solution of the electrolyte, ρ is the density of the solution, ρ_0 the density of solvent and M is the molecular weight of the solute.

The representative data in respect of Li₂SO₄ (uni-bivalent electrolyte) and NiCl₂ (bi-univalent electrolyte) have been presented in Table 3. The analysis of V_ϕ data in the light of Masson's equation reveals that the plots of V_ϕ ver-

As \sqrt{C} are linear in each case (vide Fig. 2). The values of constants V_{ϕ}^0 and S_v have been obtained from these plots by the method of least squares and the values presented in Table 4. It is seen that the values of V_{ϕ}^0 are largely positive at different temperatures which clearly suggest the presence of strong ion-solvent interactions in the solutions of both uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system. This may be attributed to the increased solvation of ions in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system. It is also observed that with the rise of temperature the values of V_{ϕ}^0 become increasingly larger which shows the increased strength of the ion-solvent interactions at elevated temperatures. This may be due to the increased solvation of ions in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system at elevated temperatures.

Table 4. Values of limiting apparent molar volume (V_{ϕ}^0), experimental slope (S_v) and partial molar volume of transfer ($\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$) for uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water and 50% formamide (FA) + water mixed solvents at different temperatures

Electrolyte	V_{ϕ}^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)		S_v (cm ³ dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-3/2})		$\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)
	0% (Water)	50%	0%	50%	
Temp. 293.15 K					
Li ₂ SO ₄	110.88	118.10	-28.04	-99.58	7.22
K ₂ SO ₄	135.81	137.53	-38.56	-142.93	1.72
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	132.84	134.64	-36.31	-88.95	1.80
NiCl ₂	169.06	176.60	-30.36	-82.31	7.54
CoCl ₂	131.53	134.53	-100.65	-92.56	3.00
MnCl ₂	186.21	187.48	-71.44	-115.60	1.27
BaCl ₂	158.19	215.76	-62.72	-86.47	57.57
SrCl ₂	182.97	221.61	-108.63	-41.08	38.64
CaCl ₂	116.66	121.89	-54.71	-91.61	5.23
MgCl ₂	134.18	198.83	-28.99	-88.09	64.65
(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Pb	191.29	215.33	-41.62	-42.10	24.04
Co(NO ₃) ₂	169.29	189.19	-23.76	-37.52	19.90
Zn(NO ₃) ₂	174.64	203.98	-18.99	-65.97	29.34
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	163.79	192.90	-47.27	-233.19	29.11
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	119.02	175.55	-69.05	-238.91	56.53
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	167.43	217.94	-16.32	-47.24	50.51
Temp. 303.15 K					
Li ₂ SO ₄	113.84	128.36	-29.71	-101.91	14.52
K ₂ SO ₄	148.30	151.82	-56.04	-154.25	3.52
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	140.74	140.97	-46.23	-96.47	0.23
NiCl ₂	172.06	199.31	-31.20	-88.92	27.25
CoCl ₂	139.14	141.32	-103.57	-101.26	2.18
MnCl ₂	192.95	198.73	-74.11	-125.99	5.78
BaCl ₂	170.56	220.94	-67.87	-92.37	50.38
SrCl ₂	190.44	225.22	-117.41	-42.50	34.78
CaCl ₂	125.57	126.39	-62.83	-96.77	0.82
MgCl ₂	143.08	210.88	-35.76	-104.53	67.80
(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Pb	198.22	224.69	-46.92	-50.90	26.47
Co(NO ₃) ₂	177.35	191.87	-27.57	-39.42	14.52
Zn(NO ₃) ₂	186.79	210.25	-25.14	-68.68	23.46
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	166.91	214.28	-48.62	-290.45	47.37
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	131.59	187.16	-76.37	-252.85	55.57
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	184.93	227.34	-25.51	-51.15	42.41

Table-3 (contd.)

	Temp. 313.15 K				
Li ₂ SO ₄	116.05	137.16	-29.95	-112.41	21.11
K ₂ SO ₄	155.93	157.92	-57.28	-164.18	1.99
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	148.98	153.14	-52.59	-109.43	4.16
NiCl ₂	179.97	202.18	-33.79	-91.04	22.21
CoCl ₂	144.78	149.99	-108.27	-111.73	5.21
MnCl ₂	196.41	204.91	-77.17	-133.89	8.50
BaCl ₂	181.89	225.21	-73.50	-90.52	43.32
SrCl ₂	199.97	228.31	-128.34	-44.52	28.34
CaCl ₂	136.38	137.00	-71.70	-99.99	0.62
MgCl ₂	154.12	226.31	-37.94	-123.36	72.19
(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Pb	210.38	240.41	-52.33	-65.56	30.03
Co(NO ₃) ₂	194.04	208.82	-36.17	-45.24	14.78
Zn(NO ₃) ₂	189.78	219.45	-27.29	-74.76	29.67
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	172.49	226.26	-60.97	-311.48	53.67
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	143.33	192.63	-82.48	-261.48	49.30
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	188.28	230.29	-26.13	-53.21	42.01

Table 5. Values of $\Delta \mu_1^{0\#}$ for 50% formamide + water and those of $\Delta \mu_2^{0\#}$ for uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolyte solutions in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents at different temperatures

Solvent	$\Delta \mu_1^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
50% Formamide (FA)			
+ Water	22.36	22.71	22.83
Electrolyte	$\Delta \mu_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Li ₂ SO ₄	57.68	62.08	69.71
K ₂ SO ₄	82.10	98.21	119.27
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	59.02	64.34	71.07
NiCl ₂	91.33	103.01	120.46
CoCl ₂	79.24	95.82	117.36
MnCl ₂	68.26	75.03	83.15
BaCl ₂	69.39	75.02	82.83
SrCl ₂	51.65	55.09	60.14
CaCl ₂	57.27	62.87	70.19
MgCl ₂	65.45	76.07	82.60
(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Pb	78.44	87.51	118.08
Co(NO ₃) ₂	62.15	66.31	70.68
Zn(NO ₃) ₂	61.70	67.13	75.72
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	89.69	97.13	101.77
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	71.03	76.05	81.42
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	66.33	72.43	79.76

On comparing the values of V_{ϕ}^0 for uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in water i.e. in purely aqueous solutions, and those in the presence of 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system it is seen that the values of V_{ϕ}^0 in the latter case are larger and that this difference varies with the nature of the electrolyte. This difference in the values of V_{ϕ}^0 is expressed in terms of volume of transfer, $\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0$ defined by the following expression :

$$\Delta \bar{V}_{tr}^0 = V_{\phi}^0(\text{MS}) - V_{\phi}^0(\text{W}) \quad (4)$$

where $V_{\phi}^0(\text{MS})$ and $V_{\phi}^0(\text{W})$ are the partial molar volumes of the solution of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in mixed solvents (50% formamide + water) and water res-

pectively. The values of $\Delta\bar{V}_r^0$ thus calculated have been presented at different temperatures in the last column of Table 4. It is seen that the values $\Delta\bar{V}_r^0$ are positive in each case and vary from electrolyte to electrolyte. The positive values of $\Delta\bar{V}_r^0$ from water to 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system may be attributed to the decrease in the volume of shrinkage because of strong interactions between the cations of the electrolytes and amide (-CONH₂) group in the formamide.

A perusal of Table 4 shows that the values of S_v are largely negative in water as well as in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system which indicate that ion-ion interactions are weak both in purely aqueous solutions as well as in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system. The fact that the values of S_v are much smaller as compared to those in purely aqueous solution shows that the ion-ion interactions in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system are much weaker as compared to those in purely aqueous solutions. This may be due to the increased solvation of the ions in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents as compared to that in water alone.

Fig. 1. Variation of $(\eta_{rel} - 1) / \sqrt{C}$ with \sqrt{C} for the solutions of NiCl₂ in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system at (□) 313.15

The viscosity data have been analyzed in the light of the transition state theory of the relative viscosity of electrolyte solutions proposed by Feakins *et al.*¹⁶. According to the theory, B coefficient is given as,

$$B = \frac{\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0}{1000} + \frac{\bar{V}_1^0}{1000} [(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}) / RT] \quad (5)$$

where \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 are the partial molar volumes of the solvent and solute respectively, $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ is the contribution per mole of solute to the free energy of activation of viscous flow of the solution and $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ is the free energy of activation per mole of the pure solvent. The values of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and there after those of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ were calculated¹⁷ using the following equations :

$$\Delta\mu_1^{0\#} = RT \ln \left(\frac{\eta_0 \bar{V}_1^0}{hN} \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_1^{0\#} + \frac{RT}{\bar{V}_1^0} [1000B - (\bar{V}_1^0 - \bar{V}_2^0)] \quad (7)$$

where h is the Planck's constant, N is the Avogadro's number, η_0 is the viscosity of the solvent, R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature.

The entropy of activation for different uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes has been calculated from the following relation¹⁶

$$\frac{d(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#})}{dT} = -\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (8)$$

The enthalpy of activation has also been calculated with the help of the following relation¹³

$$\Delta H_2^{0\#} = \Delta\mu_2^{0\#} + T\Delta S_2^{0\#} \quad (9)$$

The values of free energies of activation of viscous flow, $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$ and $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ per mole of solvent (50% formamide + water) and solute (uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes) respectively have been determined at different temperatures from eqs. (6) and (7) respectively and are presented in Table 5. It is seen that the values of $\Delta\mu_2^{0\#}$ are much larger as compared to those of $\Delta\mu_1^{0\#}$, for all the uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system; and that in each case $(\Delta\mu_2^{0\#} - \Delta\mu_1^{0\#}) > 0$. From this it follows¹⁶ that these electrolytes behave as structure-makers.

Table 6. Values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ for uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in 50% formamide (FA) + water mixed solvents at different temperatures

Electrolyte	$T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)			$\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		
	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	293.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K
Li ₂ SO ₄	-176.26	-182.27	-188.29	-118.58	-120.19	-118.58
K ₂ SO ₄	-544.85	-563.44	-582.03	-462.76	-465.23	-462.76
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	-176.57	-182.59	-188.61	-117.55	-118.25	-117.55
NiCl ₂	-427.01	-441.58	-456.14	-335.68	-338.57	-335.68
CoCl ₂	-558.68	-577.74	-596.79	-479.44	-481.92	-479.44
MnCl ₂	-218.27	-225.72	-233.16	-150.01	-150.69	-150.01
BaCl ₂	-197.05	-203.77	-210.50	-127.67	-128.75	-127.67
SrCl ₂	-124.41	-128.65	-132.90	-124.41	-128.65	-132.90
CaCl ₂	-189.29	-195.74	-202.20	-132.02	-132.88	-132.02
MgCl ₂	-251.45	-260.03	-268.61	-186.01	-183.97	-186.01
(CH ₃ COO) ₂ Pb	-581.00	-600.82	-620.64	-502.56	-513.31	-502.56
Co(NO ₃) ₂	-125.04	-129.30	-133.57	-62.89	-62.99	-62.89
Zn(NO ₃) ₂	-205.44	-212.45	-219.46	-143.74	-145.32	-143.74
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	-177.05	-183.09	-189.13	-87.36	-85.97	-87.36
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	-152.26	-157.45	-162.64	-81.22	-81.40	-81.22
Mg(NO ₃) ₂	-196.84	-203.55	-210.27	-130.51	-131.13	-130.51

The values of entropy and enthalpy of activation of viscous flow i.e. $\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ at different temperatures for the solutions of uni-bivalent and bi-univalent electrolytes in 50% formamide + water mixed solvent have been obtained from eqs. (8) and (9) respectively and presented in Table 6. It is seen that the values of $T\Delta S_2^{0\#}$ and $\Delta H_2^{0\#}$ are negative,

Fig. 2. Variation of V_{ϕ} with \sqrt{c} for the solutions of NiCl_2 in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents system at (□) 313.15 K. which suggest¹⁶ that the transition state is associated with bond making and increase in order.

Experimental

All the electrolytes used in the present study were of analytical reagent grade, which were used after drying in a vacuum oven at 110 °C for 10–12 h. The reagents were always placed in the desiccator over P_2O_5 to keep them in dry atmosphere. The standard stock solutions of the electrolytes were prepared in water and also in 50% formamide + water mixed solvents.

The densities of the solutions were measured at different temperatures (293.15, 303.15 and 313.15 K) using 5 ml pycnometers. The viscosities of the solutions were measured at the desired temperature using an Ostwald's suspended level type viscometer. Since all the flow times were greater than 100 second, the kinetic energy correction was not necessary. The density and viscosity measurement were carried out in thermostat bath, the temperature of which was controlled within accuracy of ± 0.01 K. An electronic

balance with an accuracy of 1.0×10^{-4} g was used for the mass determination.

References

1. J. I. Bhat, T. P. Mohan and C. B. Susha, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, 35, 825.
2. P. Rohdewald and M. Moldner, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1973, 77, 373.
3. Y. Marcus, "Introduction to Liquid State Chemistry", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1956.
4. J. A. Dean, "Lange's Handbook of Chemistry", McGraw Hill, New York, 1956.
5. M. L. Parmar and Ch. V. N. Rao, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1990, 29, 958.
6. S. T. Osinka, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1993, 22, 205.
7. A. Ali and A. K. Nain, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1994, 80.
8. A. Ali, A. K. Nain, N. Kumar and M. Ibrahim, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 2002, 114, 495.
9. G. Jones and M. Dole, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2950.
10. D. O. Masson, *Phil. Mag.*, 1929, 8, 218.
11. M. A. Motin, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2004, 49, 94.
12. M. L. Parmar and M. K. Guleria, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2005, 117, 351.
13. M. L. Parmar, R. K. Awasthi and M. K. Guleria, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, 43, 41.
14. M. L. Parmar, D. K. Dhiman and R. C. Thakur, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, 41, 2032.
15. H. L. Zhang, G. H. Chen and S. J. Han, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1997, 42, 526.
16. D. Fenkins, D. Freemantle and K. G. Lawrence, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1974, 70, 795.
17. S. Glasstone, K. J. Laidler and H. Eyring, "The Theory of Rate Processes", McGraw Hill, New York, 1941, 477.